

TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF VAPOUR PRESSURE OF SOLUTIONS

BY A. C. CHATTERJI AND R. P. RASTOGI

A rigorous derivation of a formula of temperature dependence of vapour pressure of solutions has been made using chemical potentials. For the binary liquid solution it has been deduced that

$$p \cdot \frac{dp}{dT} = N_1' L_1^D + N_2' L_2^D$$

where N_1' and N_2' are the molar fractions of the components 1 and 2 in the vapour phase, and L_1^D and L_2^D are the respective heats of evaporation from solution. For solutions of non-volatile solute, the change of vapour pressure with temperature is given by

$$\frac{1}{p} \cdot \frac{dp}{dT} = \frac{L_1^D}{RT^2}$$

Sackur ("Text-book of Thermochemistry and Thermodynamics", 1917, p. 248) and Planck ("Treatise on Thermodynamics", p. 1927, p. 204) have mentioned relations for the variation of pressure with temperature for solutions of non-volatile solutes. Guggenheim ("Modern Thermodynamics", 1933, p. 120) has given expressions for the change of partial pressure with temperature. The case of temperature dependence of vapour pressure of saturated solution in contact with the solid solute has also been considered (cf. Glasstone, "Thermodynamics for Chemists", 1940, p. 241). It appears from a survey of literature that a suitable expression connecting the temperature dependence of vapour pressure of solutions with the partial pressures and the molar fractions of the components is lacking. The purpose of the present paper is to derive a suitable relation applicable to various cases.

When a solution having two components, both of which are volatile, is in equilibrium with its vapour, then it has to satisfy the conditions

$$\mu_1 = \mu_1' \text{ and } \mu_2 = \mu_2'$$

where μ_1 and μ_2 are chemical potentials (partial molar free energies) of the components 1 and 2 in the liquid phase, and μ_1' and μ_2' are the corresponding chemical potentials in the vapour phase. If the temperature of the system is slightly altered keeping the two phases in equilibrium by the change of pressure and consequent change in composition, then it follows that

$$d\mu_1 = d\mu_1' \text{ and } d\mu_2 = d\mu_2'$$

The above changes in chemical potential can be represented as follows by using the well known laws of thermodynamics, assuming that the volume of the solution is very large in comparison with that of the vapour so that the change in liquid composition due to temperature variations is negligible.

$$d\mu_1 = -\bar{S}_1 dT + \bar{V}_1 dp \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$d\mu_2 = -\bar{S}_2 dT + \bar{V}_2 dp \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$d\mu_1' = -\bar{S}_1' dT + \bar{V}_1' dp + \left(\frac{d\mu_1'}{dN_1'} \right) \frac{dN_1'}{T, p} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$$d\mu_2' = -\bar{S}_2' dT + \bar{V}_2' dp + \left(\frac{d\mu_2'}{dN_2'} \right) \frac{dN_2'}{T, p} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

In these expressions $\bar{S}$ and $\bar{V}$ indicate partial molar entropy and volume respectively and N indicates molar fraction. Further, 1 or 2 placed next to a symbol refers to component 1 or 2 respectively. If the symbol, is dashed it referst to the vapour phase, otherwise to the liquid phase.

Since $d\mu_1 = d\mu_1'$ and $d\mu_2 = d\mu_2'$, we get equation (5) by equating right-hand side of equation (1) with that of (3), and obtain equation (6) in a similar way from equations (2) and (4).

$$-(S_1' - \bar{S}_1) dT + (\bar{V}_1' - \bar{V}_1) dp = - \left(\frac{d\mu_1'}{dN_1'} \right) \frac{dN_1'}{T, p} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

$$-(S_2' - \bar{S}_2) dT + (\bar{V}_2' - \bar{V}_2) dp = - \left(\frac{d\mu_2'}{dN_2'} \right) \frac{dN_2'}{T, p} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Now if we assume the vapour phase to be ideal, we have

$$\bar{V}_1' = \frac{RT}{p}; \quad \bar{V}_2' = \frac{RT}{p}$$

(cf. Guggenheim, *loc cit.*, p. 67). Also we can put

$$\bar{S}_1' - \bar{S}_1 = \frac{L_1^D}{T} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{S}_2' - \bar{S}_2 = \frac{L_2^D}{T},$$

where L_1^D and L_2^D are the respective latent heats of evaporation from solution.

Neglecting the specific volumes of the components in the liquid phase in comparison with the respective volumes of their vapour and making proper substitutions, equations (5) and (6) yield

$$-\frac{L_1^D}{T} dT + \frac{RT}{p} dp = - \left(\frac{\delta\mu_1'}{\delta N_1'} \right) \frac{dN_1'}{T, p} \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

$$-\frac{L_2^D}{T} dT + \frac{RT}{p} dp = - \left(\frac{\delta\mu_2'}{\delta N_2'} \right) \frac{dN_2'}{T, p} \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

Multiplying equation (7) by N_1' and (8) by N_2' and adding, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & - \frac{N_1' L_1^D + N_2' L_2^D}{RT} dT + (N_1' + N_2') \frac{RT}{p} dp \\ & = - \left\{ N_1' \left(\frac{\delta\mu_1'}{\delta N_1'} \right) \frac{dN_1'}{T, p} + N_2' \left(\frac{\delta\mu_2'}{\delta N_2'} \right) \frac{dN_2'}{T, p} \right\} \quad \dots \quad (9) \end{aligned}$$

But by Gibbs-Duhem relation

$$N_1' \left(\frac{\delta\mu_1'}{\delta N_1'} \right) dN_1' + N_2' \left(\frac{\delta\mu_2'}{\delta N_2'} \right) dN_2' = 0$$

and hence equation (9) yields

$$- \frac{N_1' L_1^D + N_2' L_2^D}{T} dT + (N_1' + N_2') \frac{RT}{p} dp = 0 \quad (10)$$

giving

$$\frac{1}{p} \cdot \frac{dp}{dT} = \frac{N_1' L_1^D + N_2' L_2^D}{RT^2} \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

L_1^D may be shown to be equal to $L^\circ - L_D$ from Hess's law, where L° is the heat of evaporation of pure component and L_D is the heat absorbed when 1 g. mol. of the component is added to a large volume of the solution.

For a solution of non-volatile solute (component 2) $N_2' = 0$ and $N_1' = 1$. Hence for such cases (11) becomes

$$\frac{1}{p} \cdot \frac{dp}{dT} = \frac{L_1^D}{RT^2} \quad (12)$$

The integration of the above equation, assuming L_1^D not to vary with temperature, yields

$$\ln p = -\frac{L_1^D}{RT} + \text{constant} \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

From equation (13) it is clear that plot of $\log p$ against $1/T$ should be a straight line within a small range of temperature. This explains the straight line plot obtained by Roehl (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1291) in case of several solutions. We have also obtained similar results in case of several aqueous solutions of electrolytes (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 597). If L_1^D does not differ much from the latent heat of vaporisation of the pure solvent, the straight line will be parallel to the corresponding curve for the solvent as has been observed by Roehl (*loc. cit.*). On the other hand, if L_1^D differs much from the latent heat of vaporisation of the pure solvent, this will not be the case. This particularly happens in solutions of hydrated salts (cf. Ewing, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 1293).

The authors have great pleasure to thank Dr. B. N. Srivastava F. N. I. for numerous discussions which they had with him in the course of this work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY, LUCKNOW.

Received September 21, 1951.